

EVALUATION OF BRAIDING AS A METHOD FOR THE MANUFACTURING OF COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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ABSTRACT

Composite pressure vessels are nowadays mostly manufactured by wet-filament winding. This is a well-established technology, but future challenges call for the investigation of alternative manufacturing methods. The proposed large-scale use of compressed natural gas and compressed hydrogen gas in mobile applications leads to a high demand for safe and economic lightweight and high-pressure gas storage. Challenges arise from the requirements of long-term performance, favourable crash behaviour and the demand of high volume production.

In comparison to filament-wound structures, over-braided shells are attributed with the following properties: improved damage tolerance, improved impact resistance and the possibility of lower manufacturing cycle times. Furthermore, opportunities of different fibre angle distributions and fibre architectures may result in advantages for the design of composite pressure vessels. These promising attributes stimulated a research project for the evaluation of braiding as a method for the manufacturing of a composite pressure vessel. This project encompasses braiding trials, material tests, manufacturing simulations, material modelling and structural analysis. The main results are an improved understanding of the process limits of braiding, stiffness and strength data for initial design purposes and improved simulation and analysis tools for the detailed structural design with finite element analysis. This contribution gives an overview of the research project and discusses the key results. It will display which processing factors and limits require consideration for applying the braiding process to the production of pressure vessels in automotive applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Light pressure vessels made of fibre-reinforced plastics (FRP) can be used for the storage of gaseous hydrogen on fuel cell drives. Currently, the fuel cell drive system is being developed as one possible alternative for propulsion systems of future vehicle generations. Fibre-reinforced pressure vessels allow a weight reduction of more than 200% compared to metallic containers. However, this is offset by a threefold price increase. . A reduction of the process and material costs by a more precise interpretation and prediction is therefore essential [1].

In the state of the art, such pressure vessels are manufactured in relatively small quantities using the wet filament winding process with carbon fibres and a thermosetting resin as matrix material. However, the winding process is subject to restrictions on the achievable fibre deposition angles and the production speed in the process.

In order for high-pressure vessels to remain attractive as an alternative to competing energy storage systems, improvements in the design and manufacturing technology are required. This can be achieved by choosing an efficient production process and better material utilization.

The braiding technique in combination with resin transfer moulding (RTM) is an alternative approach to the wet filament winding process. It is fully automatable [2] and suitable to achieve short cycle times for the fibre lay-up and thereby a higher productivity in the mass production [7].

Furthermore, braided composite structures also have excellent failure characteristics. Compared to metal parts, braided composites part can enable a weight reduction of up to 70 % [9]. A superior failure characteristic for impact loads in pressure vessels through integration of braided fabrics has already been demonstrated [3].

2 MOTIVATION AND APPROACH

2.1 Motivation

To examine the previous mentioned aspects, a calculation model for the design of overbraided pressure vessels is developed. This is done similarly to the well-established procedure of simulating filament wound pressure vessels.

The braiding process strongly depends on the desired product. The machinery must be chosen according to the application with respect to e.g. the size and number of fibre carriers. In automotive applications the dimensions are limited to a certain range due to available build space in the car. This paper will show which parameters must be considered when setting up a production line for braided pressure vessels. This is performed given the typical pressure vessel dimensions in automotive applications.

2.2 Approach

The projects approach for the manufacturing of the preform is to braid straight onto the braiding mandrel. This allows a one-step near net shape preforming process. Furthermore, the fibre angle can be locally adjusted to the loads. Previous analysis, which focused on the characteristics of typical fibre angles in the braiding process, showed that braided vessels are an alternative to filament wound vessels regarding material efficiency as well as storage density. Taking into account simulation and analytical investigations, a general feasibility of the overbraiding manufacturing process can be determined [5,6].

Fibres take up main loads in the direction of fibre orientation. This must be considered especially with regard to the loads and fibre orientations in the dome part of the vessel. Pressure vessels produced via filament winding show an increasing fibre angle towards the dome end whereas braided structure shows a decreasing fibre angle. This results not only in a different laminate setup but also comes in play when designing the dome shape [4, 5].

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS AND ANALYSIS

Experiments and simulation were performed to determine if the previous assumption, concepts and analytical approaches could be verified.

3.1 Braiding process trials and simulation

Standard carbon fibre linear densities available on the market range between 200 tex₇ and 2400 tex. In consideration of pricing 200 and 400 tex were excluded because they are twice as expensive as 800 or 1600 tex fibres. In addition there is a direct correlation between fibre density, the number of fibres needed to cover a given diameter and the machine invest in relation to numbers of braiding bobbins. A lower yarn density translates into a higher number of fibres for full coverage of the vessel which leads to a higher machine invest. In addition, a higher fibre count leads to higher productivity (kg/h lay-up of fibre) and is therefore generally desirable.

As an input parameter for the simulation, the radial braiding machine's process limits have to be determined. This is realised by overbraiding a standardized dome shape and characterizing the braiding results. The goal is to ensure a uniform, closed braided structure and avoid slipping and jamming in the dome shape region (cp. Figure 1). The results of the experiments on the standardized dome shape were used to design a dome shape adapted to the braiding process characteristics and typical fibre angle distributions.

Figure 1: Standardized dome shape for characterization of slipping and jamming effects in the overbraiding process.

To support the braiding trials a finite element method (FEM) model of the braiding process was set up and validated against results from the machinery (cp. Figure 2). The aim of introducing FEM to the design process is to decrease the number of experiments and allow optimization of the possible fibre angles as an input parameter for the structural simulation. Analytical approaches already show good results and can help in the design process [5], however, fail to display all relevant parameters in the braiding process, such as fibre tension. The FEM-simulation runs based on the commercial simulation software ABAQUS. To reduce the time for setting up the simulation model, scripts were implemented to allow a semi-automated design of simulation models.

Figure 2: Overbraiding of pressure vessel geometry and simulation in FEM

3.3 Structural analyses

The structural analysis for filament-wound composite pressure vessels by finite element analysis is well-established [10]. For overbraided structures, important differences are considered. The characteristics of the braiding process result in specific fibre angle and layer thickness distributions [4]. We enhanced our modelling software to consider this.

The braiding process also leads to a fibre architecture that shows maximized interlacing of the fibres. Classical laminate theory models this less accurately. While enhanced models for braided structures are proposed in literature, we employ empirical correction factors to estimate the effects of braiding in our models.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Investigations on using the FEM process simulation showed that the setup-time for the models can be significantly decreased by the use of scripting. However, computing times for the simulation of the process itself are too high to use the FEM as a tool for optimization. In this research project, no significant benefit was gained for the design process of the pressure vessel.

Braiding experiments on the dome shape indicated a qualitative match of the experimental results to the analytical formulas for calculation of the braiding angle. The braiding angle significantly decreases with the lower diameter (cp. Figure 3).

Figure 3: Dome shape and characteristics of the braiding angle on the dome contour

The braiding trials showed that the deposit width and thus the linear density of the fibres influence the slipping behaviour. The greater the width of depositing fibres compared to its initial width, the higher the tendencies of slipping on the dome geometry. The crimp of the fabric was also identified as a significant influence parameter for the behaviour of the braid layup. Table 1 shows an overview of significant design variables that have an influence on the slipping behaviour of the braid being placed on the mandrel.

	Dome shape		Spreading of fibre		N° of crossover points	
Slipping of fibres	high	low	high	low	high	low

Table 1: Qualitative effects on the slipping behaviour of the fibres during braid lay-up

The results of our structural simulations suggest two important differences between filament wound and overbraided composite pressure vessels:

1. The optimum contour shape of overbraided vessels is not the well-established Isotensoid shape as for filament wound vessels
2. The changed fibre angle distributions resulting from the braiding process offer opportunities for laminate optimizations that are not available for filament wound structures.

These effects can be recognized when comparing the results of the FEM stress evaluation for a vessel with inappropriate dome shape and laminate lay-up (Figure 4) with the results for an optimized

vessel design (Figure 5). The optimized vessel shows a reduced variation of the stresses and thus the opportunity for an economical design.

Figure 4: FEM stress evaluation for vessel with inappropriate dome shape and laminate lay-up.

Figure 5: FEM stress evaluation for vessel with optimized dome shape and laminate lay-up.

5 CONCLUSION AND PROSPECTS

The limits of the braiding process for the manufacturing of composite pressure vessels were successfully determined. It was shown that especially the dome geometry is of great importance for

the processing. Depending on fibre density, braiding core material and geometry, general relationships between parameters have been identified and documented. To compensate for the limitations in the braiding process with respect to slip off the braid on the core, lifting or jamming of the braid, a change of dome shape is recommended. Typical deposition paths have been validated on the modified pressure vessel. To collect data for a differentiated angular and laminate construction, these experiments were run with different starting angles in the cylinder. For the braiding angle characteristics in the dome limitations and gradients with respect to the maximum and minimum possible target angle were determined. The validated process parameters were used as input for structural simulation.

Regarding the economic feasibility of the braiding as a production method for pressure vessels, the bobbin exchange was identified as crucial parameter when considering the overall steps for preform production. It is a key factor for the productivity as it increases the downtime when changing braiding bobbins.

A follow up project with regard to the bobbin exchange has therefore been initiated. The project called “AuFaWe” will pursue a solution for the automated change of bobbins. The approach is to compile existing technologies from automation and textile technology to implement the automated bobbin change on braiding machinery (cp. Figure 4).

Figure 4: Concept for the automation of the bobbin exchange for braiding machinery.

In order to make the existing technology available for both new and already existing machines a modular bobbin change concept will be integrated. The technical challenge is the small space which is available for integration and the complex machine dynamics of the braiding machinery to which the exchange system has to function. For technical and economic validation of the system, a full-scale prototype will be developed and tested. The overall goal of the project is to increase braiding machine productivity by decreasing downtime due to bobbin exchange by 50%.

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